

VALKYRIES

D1.18 Protocols for innovators M24

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides methodological protocols for innovators to meet compliance requirements while developing technological solutions for first responders and within similar sectors.

The deliverable constitutes the updated version of the D1.4 released in M12. The new content with respect to the D1.4 has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

It takes into account the evolution of the ethical legal framework, as analysed in D3.3, and the cybersecurity advances in literature for compliance purposes. To this end, guidelines and recommendations are developed and included in tailored sections of the DEMO released in M24 under the T1.5 activities.

2. Identification

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3. Document and Project Scope

This is the **final** version of the Protocols for Innovators **already submitted as a draft at M12** aiming to drive the ethical-legal compliance in Research & Development & Innovation sectors.

Starting from the procedures developed in VALKYRIES, the document aims to share a pathway towards the so-called accountability and **Responsible Research and Innovation** in each step of the life-cycle of the development despite of the type of the designed technology or solution.

3.1. Project Overview

The Deliverable combines the research and compliance overview of the VALKYRIES ecosystem. It shows how regulation, standardisation, and compliance are fully integrated by the application of the principle of accountability.

3.2. Document Structure

Starting from the VALKYRIES ethical-legal compliance experience, the document firstly illustrates how the evolution of the regulatory framework, and the standardisation of technical steps are impacting on the compliance activities, then it provides protocols to drive innovators towards the complexity of the applicable framework.

3.3. Requirements compliance matrix

Description of the requirements can be consulted in D2.7 – Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases document. Table below presents the WP1 Traceability Matrix.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project pilots)
REQ_BASE_T5.1_3	NA	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9	D1.18	Recommended	Inspection: guidelines fully extracted

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix

4. Methodology

This Report has been developed into two different steps covering all the duration of the project. At M12 and a revised version here in M24 have followed the same methodology.

In particular, considering that pioneering solutions shall adhere to the intricate set of regulations in place, it has been crucial during the VALKYRIES project to accurately ascertain the specific legal prerequisites and formulate strategies for managing impending ones. This involved taking into account the dynamic shifts within the regulatory framework that impact sectors involved in research, development, and innovation sectors.

Consequently, it became imperative to create an initial overview of legally relevant documents, as provided in the following paragraphs and to update them in light of the new initiatives at EU level, at least with a comparative and practical approach, as defined also in D3.3 submitted at M20.

This was done to evaluate the following:

- The pertinence of chosen legal undertakings and the formulation of interpretive principles to address any gaps.
- The influence of regulatory and legal barriers on innovation and the degree of their impact.
- The potential of EU legislative proposals that are yet to be enacted to already serve as valuable interpretive benchmarks for strategies concerning, especially, data management and data-driven solutions.

As anticipated an updated cross-field analysis has been performed and reported in D3.3, as a follow up of the first version of this report aiming to shape the interplay between the current compliance requirements, the developed legal and technical standards, and the regulatory insights relevant to the VALKYRIES ecosystem and for – more generally – innovators.

The described workflow is part of a more general approach, developed within the research line ETHOS ETHics and law with and fOr reSearch (www.lider-lab.it) at LIDER Lab, DIRPOLIS Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, that is remarkably applicable to the VALKYRIES activities.

Considering the multitude of initiatives introduced by the EU Commission, encompassing digitalization, data-driven processes, and innovation, it is evident that these efforts are aimed at shaping an all-encompassing digital society. As a result, all services and products within the EU's data-driven economy must align with both the ethical-legal framework and the demands of the market. This underscores the inescapable integration of such entities within the broader digital landscape.

Indeed, to comprehend the current societal ramifications of research, development, and innovation (R&D&I), adopting a bottom-up approach proves highly advantageous.

This approach commences with an examination of the allocation of roles and responsibilities, as well as an analysis of compliance obligations. The intention is to determine the applicability of existing standardization mechanisms to the specific context, or whether additional endeavours are necessary to establish shared practices and solutions.

Examining the current interaction among compliance activities, recognition of shared methodologies, and legal benchmarks, along with active participation in regulatory discussions,

serves to formulate approaches that, in conjunction with technical standards, advance principles such as human dignity and other fundamental EU values. These combined efforts are geared towards fostering a more inclusive societal framework.

Therefore, guidelines including operative checklists and protocols are completing the previous analysis, including the ones on ethics and diversity reported in D1.19, driving researchers and innovators both in the digital transition of traditional services and products development life-cycles and in advancing technical frontiers by adopting a responsible and accountable approach by design and by default.

5. Ethical legal compliance and the regulatory framework

Ethical-legal compliance activities play a crucial role in the Research & Development & Innovation sectors, where innovators are the main agents. In fact, in parallel to the technical steps, each technological solution shall be compliant with the applicable framework *by design* and *by default*. To this end, the so-called risk-based approach governs the implementation of identified organisational and technical measures considered as proper ones to meet the ethical requirements and to fulfil the legal obligations. In particular, the innovators shall assess how their idea is impacting on fundamental rights and therefore they shall comply with the provisions stated by applicable framework to protect them. Compliance activities are usually consisting of the introduction of technical and organisational measures in the life-cycle of the technology development either to mitigate the risks of their infringement of fundamental rights or to fulfil the stated obligations. The innovators shall be able to demonstrate to have adopted the described methodology (i.e. accountability). In case of breach of stated obligations, they could be sanctioned by the competent authority and considered as liable for possible occurred damages.

Beyond the illustrated premises, the ethical-legal compliance process is particularly complex, if we consider the following barriers:

- Innovators are not always familiar with fundamental rights protection as they are interpreted by the ethical-legal framework.
- The ethical-legal binding framework is often unclear also for experts because the state of the art is still evolving and national implementations may limit a harmonised sectorial approach.

In particular, the EU Regulations, that are directly binding among EU Member States, could leave room for national implementations and interpretations. This could limit a harmonised interpretation of a given provision. The EU Directives, indeed, become effective in a given EU Member States only after a national legislative implementation, potentially determining 27 different procedures to interpret the same principle.

- Regarding soft law regulations, such as recommendations, guidelines etc., even if they are non-binding, as they aim to address interpretative issues, they could contribute to the state of the art on a given topic. In fact, to follow specific soft law provisions could help to demonstrate an accountable approach, especially if they have been adopted by supra-national institutional organisations (e.g. European Data Protection Board -EDPB-, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, other groups of experts), or national ones (like Data Protection Authorities), or as a self-regulation instrument by private companies in a given sector (e.g. certificates under article 42 GDPR). Such a standardisation activity regarding interpretative gaps could stimulate the ongoing legislative debates, but - at the same time - it could arise several procedural differences to meet the same ethical-legal requirements.

This document aims to identify methodological solutions by developing protocols for innovators in order to facilitate the compliance activities starting from the ethical-legal issues arisen in the VALKYRIES ecosystem.

From this perspective, this protocol illustrates actions that are supposed to be undertaken by innovators to be compliant with the binding framework and accountable respect to the non-binding one. The adoption of the following protocols will also facilitate the development of best

practices that could contribute to a more standardised and harmonised development of the ethical-legal framework in the future, especially in cross-border contexts.

5.1. Overview of the regulatory initiatives for R&D&I

In the last years the EU adopted several strategies to boost innovation. In particular, all the initiatives are based on distributing roles and responsibilities in order to undertake an impact assessment of the technological solution on fundamental rights protected by the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights.

The introduction of a risk-based approach to drive innovation constitutes the common core of the legislative initiatives that have been drafted in the last years. However, the plurality of aspects relating to the ethical-legal compliance are not always addressed with the same technical and organisational measures. In fact, R&D&I sectors shall address several challenges from the ones related to common market and business development, to the ones related to the data-driven approach to open data, data spaces development and privacy.

The table below includes an overview of the regulatory framework impacting on the ethical legal challenges related to R&D&I sectors.

Act	Comments
Regulation (EU) no 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (CTR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since January 31st 2023. - More uniform rules for clinical trials across the EU to enhance international collaboration among different partners. - Use of a unique IT infrastructure (the CTIS portal) to submit the requested documents. - Principle of prior authorization for clinical trials. - National Ethical Committees (ECs) are tasked with carrying out a scientific and ethical review of the documentation submitted. - Member States have a certain leeway as far as the implementation of the discipline concerning the National ECs to make it compliant with the CTR.
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since May 25th 2018. - Room for national implementations for research (article 89). - Room for national implementation for “sensitive data” processing (article 9). - First binding provision on automated decision-making processing (article 22).
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since 2019. - Processing different non-personal datasets could make them considered as personal data.
Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since May 21st 2021. The deadline for the national implementation of it is 26 may 2024. - The former Directive had national implementations in each Member State.

Act	Comments
<p>2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (MDR)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local ethics committees developed own procedures, developing barriers to harmonised application of the law in action. - Legal gap between approval procedures for clinical trials and non-clinical studies. - The MDR tries to make the certification procedures for medical devices more harmonised across the EU - It tries to increase the level of safety and security of the devices by adding more detailed obligations on manufacturers and on Notified Bodies, the organizations which are agreed by the European Commission and that must certify that the medical device is safe and secure for the EU market. - It also adds post-market surveillance duties and an obligation for manufacturers to get an insurance and to have enough resources for eventual product liability trials. - It also puts in place a unique database for all the medical devices in the EU, EUDAMED.
<p>Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act, DGA)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since September 2023. - Field of application mainly refers to public sector, but it aims to set-up common European data spaces in strategic domains, involving both private and public players, for health, environment, energy, agriculture, mobility, finance, manufacturing, public administration. - National policies for data altruism.
<p>Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It specifies the role and mandate of ENISA. - It introduces a European system for the certification of the IT security of devices connected to the Internet and other digital products and services.
<p>Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 COM/2022/454 final (Cyber-resilience act)</p>	<p>This proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lists down rules to place on the market IoT objects which comply with harmonized cybersecurity standards. Article 1(a) - sets “[e]ssential requirements for the design, development and production of products with digital elements, and obligations for economic operators in relation to these products with respect to cybersecurity” Article 1(b) - lays down Essential requirements for vulnerability handling concerning the cybersecurity level for the whole life-cycle of an IoT. Article 1(c)

Act	Comments
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -and creates rules post market surveillance and enforcement of the above-cited requirements. Article 1(d).
<p>Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending certain union legislative acts COM/2021/206 final (AI Act)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Still at proposal level. - It recalls the Data Strategy initiatives (GDPR, DGA etc.), but players are not completely overlapping in terms of roles and responsibilities. - It is the first document to define AI as AI system, which mainly refers to software. - AI systems could be high or low risk. Depending on that, the AI creators will have either more or less duties and compliance obligations to respect. - There will be the creation of AI specific Notified Bodies (as in the MDR) which will need to assess the security, the safety and respect of human rights of a high-risk AI system. - The AI act, which should be passed in autumn 2023, will also set the framework for national AI bodies which will coordinate at the EU level.
<p>Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on machinery products COM/2021/202 final</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It refers to safety of products not based on AI techniques. - It recalls the above-mentioned legislative initiatives, but players are not completely overlapping in terms of roles and responsibilities.
<p>Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entered into force on 24 April 2011, and it was expected to be transposed to national law by the EU Member States by 25 October 2013. - The Directive is principally addressed to patients, as it aims to regulate the conditions under which such private players can travel to other EU countries for medical care. In this context, it tackles with the need for a secure and efficient cooperation between national healthcare systems across Europe, hence it encourages Member States to adopt measures respecting data privacy of patients while facilitating the exchange of health data.
<p>European Health Data Space Proposal (EHDS, secondary use of health data for research, COM/2022/197 final)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Still at a proposal level. - The EDHS is the evolution of the previously mentioned Patients' Rights Directive. One of its two main objectives is to make EU citizens able to use common and interoperable health data records across the EU. - The EDHS tries to address and to discipline the secondary use of health data for research by setting up a system of requests and permits in order to access a research institution health data.

Act	Comments
Regulation (EU) 2014/910 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Applicable since 17 September 2014.- It is intended to provide for a securely and smoothly operation system of interaction between public and private players, including business enterprises and citizens, across EU.

Table 2 – Overview of the regulatory initiatives for R&D&I

6. Ethical legal compliance and standardisation

Ethical-legal compliance is a complex and continuous process where -according to a predetermined and distributed system of roles and responsibilities- innovators must introduce safeguards and procedures in the technical development of a given solution, in order to mitigate risks to infringe fundamental rights and/or to accomplish to specific binding provisions.

Ethical-legal compliance is strictly connected to regulation and standardisation processes. In fact, the binding dimension of the statutory law for innovators is completed by the global character of the technical standards that strongly impact on the law in action and, more generally, on soft law tools. However, considering the regulatory barriers identified in the previous paragraph, the case-by-case approach could still be combined with a more harmonised approach aiming to identify the ethical legal dimension as a part of the development of technical standards.

The VALKYRIES consortium is focusing on these profiles, combining the strict compliance of the project activities with the ambition to develop standardised procedure aiming to develop a *modus operandi* suitable to be applied in any R&D activity.

6.1. Overview of the Ethical-legal Related Standards

The table below identifies for each regulatory initiative the good practices, standards and tools that have been developed to achieve a higher level of accountability.

They are not binding and they are addressing only specific profiles, but they cover interpretative gaps, addressing how to comply with ethics by design and by default.

Act	Legal standards and tools
Regulation (EU) no 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (CTR)	ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	ENISA 2019 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/risk-level-tool/risk CNIL 2019 https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle/ia-comment-etre-en-conformite-avec-le-rgpd ENISA 2020 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme/ CNIL 2022 https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle/ia-comment-etre-en-conformite-avec-le-rgpd ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14	COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL Guidance on the Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-

Act	Legal standards and tools
November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union	personal data in the European Union https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2019:250:FIN
Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (MDR)	<p>ENISA 2020 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme/</p> <p>ENISA https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/critical-information-infrastructures-and-services/health/good-practices-for-the-security-of-healthcare-services#/</p> <p>EU Commission https://health.ec.europa.eu/medical-devices-sector/new-regulations/guidance-mdcg-endorsed-documents-and-other-guidance_en</p>
Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)	ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts COM/2021/206 final (AI Act)	<p>ENISA 2023 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/cybersecurity-of-ai-and-standardisation/@@download/fullReport</p> <p>CNIL 2022 https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle/ia-comment-etre-en-conformite-avec-le-rgpd</p> <p>ALTAI 2020 https://digitalstrategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment</p>
Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare	<p>- Commission Delegated Decision of 10 March 2014 setting out criteria and conditions that European Reference Networks and healthcare providers wishing to join a European Reference Network must fulfil, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32014D0286&from=EN ;</p> <p>- Commission Implementing Decision of 10 March 2014</p>

Act	Legal standards and tools
	<p>setting out criteria for establishing and evaluating European Reference Networks and their Members and for facilitating the exchange of information and expertise on establishing and evaluating such Networks, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32014D0287&from=EN;</p> <p>- Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety Guidelines on Patient Summary (3 June 2021), https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/guidelines-patient-summary_en</p>
<p>Regulation (EU) 2014/910 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC</p>	<p>-Commission Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (C(2019)800) of 6 February 2019 (and the Annex https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019H0243&rid=2)</p>

Table 3 – Overview of the **ethical-legal related** standards

6.2. Cybersecurity Issues

Cybersecurity analysis should be developed since design level in order to anticipate the risks and challenges that may emerge in the subsequent deployment of the technologies. This is crucial as all the R&D&I technologies are connected online and therefore are exposed and maybe vulnerable to cybersecurity risks, which include the cases of falling victim to cybercrime or to disclose personal information online.

Although cybersecurity has started to be analysed and regulated at European level since early 2010s, there is a difference between the legislative measures adopted at European level as regards the protection of data, and in particular personal data, and the safeguards to be set up on the level of networks and infrastructures. The case of data breach is covered by the GDPR legislation, whereas the security incidents are covered by the Network and Information Security Directive (NIS) n. 2016/1148 and the new NIS 2 Directive 2022/2555. However, these two directives only apply to the so-called essential and important entities, i.e. medium and large companies that provide the services listed in the Annex to the directive. The companies that do not fall in the sectors or do not have such dimension are not covered by the directive, and are left without specific guidelines to set up their cybersecurity framework.

In 2022, the EU bodies decided to fill this gap and presented the Cyber-resilience Act which identifies a set of basic security and vulnerability requirements that can apply to any product with digital elements. Moreover, specific additional requirements were then proposed for the

health sector, and in particular for Electronic health records and wellness devices in the Proposal for a European Health Data Space.

Act	Comments
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	<p>Art 24 refers to the need to adopt technical and organisational measures that take into account the risks for the rights and freedoms of natural persons.</p> <p>Art. 25 requires that the controller shall implement privacy by design and privacy by default.</p> <p>Art 32 requires that the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk</p> <p>Art. 33 provides for a specific procedure in case of data breach</p>
EU Directive 2016/1148 concerning measures for a high level of common security of network and information systems across the Union	<p>The directive (now repealed) lays down measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To achieve a high common level of security of network and information systems within the Union - to improve the functioning of the internal market <p>It requires Member States to adopt a national strategy and to designate the national competent authorities and at least one competent CSIRT for the essential services. It also requires that operators of essential services (OESs) and digital service providers (DSPs) to comply with established security-related requirements.</p>
Directive (EU) 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity (NIS 2)	<p>The directive aims at</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase the level of cyber-resilience of a comprehensive set of businesses operating in the European Union across all relevant sectors - Reduce inconsistencies in resilience across the internal market in the sectors already covered by the directive - Improve the level of joint situational awareness and the collective capability to prepare and respond <p>The Directive distinguish between essential and important operators which are subject to the same requirements as regards security and incident notification, but are subject to different monitoring activities by the relevant authorities.</p>
Proposal for a Regulation on cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements - Cyber resilience Act	<p>Rules for the placing on the market of products with digital elements to ensure the cybersecurity of such products;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - essential requirements for the design, development and production of products with digital elements, and obligations for economic operators in relation to these products with respect to cybersecurity; - essential requirements for the vulnerability handling processes put in place by manufacturers to ensure the cybersecurity of products with digital elements during the

Act	Comments
	<p>whole life cycle, and obligations for economic operators in relation to these processes;</p> <p>- rules on market surveillance and enforcement of the above-mentioned rules and requirements.</p>
<p>Proposal for a Regulation on European Health Data Space</p>	<p>Annex II - Requirements: general, interoperability and safety</p> <p>Among the security requirements:</p> <p>Authentication-related accessibility (based on professional rights and qualifications) with the possibility of limitations</p> <p>Registration of internal activity</p> <p>Inclusion of authentication with digital signature</p> <p>Control of data retention period</p>

Table 4 – Overview of the regulatory initiatives developing cybersecurity profiles

In order to avoid incurring into security incidents and data breach it is important that the entity that is in charge of designing and developing a R&D&I technologies takes into account the requirements and the procedures set up by the NIS 2 Directive, as well as by the GDPR. As a matter of fact, it is possible that not all security incidents will involve personal data, thus be qualified as data breaches, but some of the measures that are aimed at protecting the data running on the network will also be suitable for the protection of the network security itself.

It is possible to identify a set of steps in order to prevent and react to potential risks. The process is iterative and can be adapted to the specific type of processing carried out in the R&D&I at stake.

The table below illustrates five steps that should be addressed in order to prevent and, in case of incidents, react to a problem. It is important to clarify that depending on the type of attack, different procedure may be applicable: in case of data breach, the point of reference for the entity will be the national data protection authority, while in case of security incident, the point of reference will be national authority or the CSIRT¹ set up at national level.

The following guidelines for R&D&I can be extracted beyond the first response sector in order to *Prevent, Detect, Evaluate, Mitigate* the consequences of data breach/incident, and *Communicate* it to the proper organisations.

Prevent the data breach/incident
<p>Responsibilities and governance (<i>i.e.</i> identification of a point of contact for cybersecurity)</p> <p>Education (cybersecurity training)</p> <p>Data minimization approach in the all life-cycle (<i>i.e.</i> data collection, data access, data archives, ...);</p> <p>Policy definitions (rules of behaviour when using ICT environment, equipment and services);</p>

¹ CSIRT: Computer Security Incident Response team. Pursuant Art. 10 NIS 2 Directive, each Member State is required to set up a CSIRT.

Prevent the data breach/incident

Introduction of technical and organisational measures including:

- Secure backups and deletion;
- Protection of mobile devices (passwords, antivirus, encryption, updates and patches, ...);
- Use of Secure Networks (VPN);
- Upgrading software and hardware ;
- Management of contractors (list of minimum cybersecurity requirements, monitoring activity, include NDA or confidentiality clauses);

Resilience (incident response);

Audit

Access Control

Monitoring and Detection

Table 5 – R&D&I Guidelines – Prevent the data breach/incident

Detect the security incident

1. Identifying the security incident: the gap between breach and detection

Tools: Logging and monitoring; Intrusion detection and alerting.

2. Understand the root cause: the breach was caused by a firewall with an open port, malware on the system, an e-mail phishing attack, outdated anti-virus software, or a system breach.

Tools: Forensic analysis, Audit

3. Registration and detailed documentation

4. Escalation and reporting (internally).

Table 6 – R&D&I Guidelines – Detect the security incident

Evaluate the incident

Verify :

- Type of services affected
- Types of data affected (personal data or not)
- Number of people affected
- Type of damage (material and non-material damage)
- What is the length of time between the breach/incident and detection
- Assess risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects

Table 7 – R&D&I Guidelines – Evaluate the incident

Mitigate

Take immediate action (e.g., isolate the affected system, change passwords, shut down breached web pages, etc.)

Ensure that systems are out of harm's way (fix the problem)

Document all the way through

Take corrective action (to prevent a new breach)

Updating policies and procedures

Post-incident assessment

Table 8 – R&D&I Guidelines – Mitigate the incident

Communicate the incident/ the data breach

1. Can the incident be qualified as a security incident according to Art 6(6) NIS 2 Directive?

“incident” means an event compromising the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, network and information systems;

Communicate the incident/ the data breach

No -> Go to question N.3

Yes -> Go to next question

2. Can the incident be qualified as significant incident according to Art. 21 (3) NIS 2 Directive? An incident shall be considered to be significant if: (a) it has caused or is capable of causing severe operational disruption of the services or financial loss for the entity concerned; (b) it has affected or is capable of affecting other natural or legal persons by causing considerable material or non-material damage.

No -> The company is not obliged to report the incident to CSIRT. (However, Art. 30 NIS 2 Directive provides for the possibility of voluntary notification to CSIRT in case of incidents, cyber threats and near misses).

Yes -> Company should notify the CSIRT according to the following timeline:

Within 24 hours of becoming aware of the significant incident : Notify the CSIRT with an early warning (indicate whether the significant incident is suspected of being caused by unlawful or malicious acts or could have a cross-border impact)

Within 72 hours of becoming aware of the significant incident : Notify the CSIRT with incident notification (update early warning and indicate an initial assessment of the significant incident, including its severity and impact, as well as, where available, the indicators of compromise)

Within one month after incident notification: notify the CSIRT with a final report (including a detailed description of the incident, including its severity and impact, the type of threat or root cause that is likely to have triggered the incident, applied and ongoing mitigation measures, where applicable, the cross-border impact of the incident).

3. Can the incident be qualified as a data breach according to art. 4 (12) GDPR?

'data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.

No -> The company is not obliged to report the data breach to the DPA. However, the company is required to document any personal data breaches, comprising the facts relating to the personal data breach, its effects and the remedial action taken according to Art. 33(5) GDPR.

Yes -> go to next question.

4. Can the data breach be qualified as likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons according to art. 33 (2) GDPR?

No -> The company is not obliged to report the data breach to the DPA.

Yes -> Company should notify the DPA according to the following timeline:

Within 72 hours of becoming aware of the data breach : Notify the DPA the event (describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned; communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained; describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach; describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller

Communicate the incident/ the data breach

to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects).

5. Is the data breach likely to pose high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals?

No-> the company is not obliged to inform the data subjects of the data breach.

YES -> the company is obliged to notify the data subject of the breach without undue delay according to Art. 34(3) GDPR.²

Table 9 – R&D&I Guidelines – Communicate the incident

These guidelines will be embedded in the DEMO as well.

² Note that no question is provide as regards the notification to the CSIRT about the security incident as the decision to communicate to the public the incident lies mostly on the CSIRT and the national competent authority. See Art. 23 (7) NIS 2 Directive : "7. Where public awareness is necessary to prevent a significant incident or to deal with an ongoing significant incident, or where disclosure of the significant incident is otherwise in the public interest, a Member State's CSIRT or, where applicable, its competent authority, and, where appropriate, the CSIRTs or the competent authorities of other Member States concerned, may, after consulting the entity concerned, inform the public about the significant incident or require the entity to do so".

7. Protocols for innovators

Considering the above-illustrated aspects, the following protocols, including innovator-friendly check-lists could be extracted to facilitate the adoption of an accountable approach in each step of the innovative solution development, namely: 1. Preparatory activities; 2. Development; 3. Application/Usage. A preliminary document has been released at M12, a DEMO has also been published at M12 in the VALKYRIES website <https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Demo.html> and illustrated to the ethical and legal workshops and dissemination events where stakeholders provided inputs and suggestions.

A revised version is released and embedded to the platform developed in D1.5.

7.1. Preparatory activities

This step refers to the *design* of the innovative solution and it determines the beginning of the life-cycle of the solution. Preparatory activities could be embedded in a proposal /draft of project that includes the proof of concept of the technology solution. In that context, innovators shall assess if and how the development could impact on fundamental rights protection and how to comply with the corresponding ethical-legal framework. This step is needed both for *management* and *technical* purposes. In fact, both human and technical resources as well as time shall be allocated to the ethical-legal compliance.

To better achieve a realistic evaluation of the compliance activities, innovators need to firstly identify the targeted group / end-users as well as the different applications/uses of the technological solution in order to provide a first screening of the applicable ethical legal framework and select the main issues that shall be addressed as well as the obligations they need to accomplish to during the development. Two dimensions shall be analysed: i) the impact during the development of the technology (*compliance by design*) and ii) the impact once on the market (*compliance by default*).

The following check-list could be identified.

A) Compliance by design. In order to develop/test the solution:

1. Do you need to involve human participants?

If not, an information sheet including the privacy information (see below) is required under articles 11 ff GDPR, and an informed consent could be required under the national legal framework.

If yes, are they belonging to vulnerable groups (i.e. patients, children, employees etc.)?

- An ethical committee approval is required for clinical trials.
- An ethical committee approval could be binding under national/sectorial legal frameworks even for non-clinical trials.
- Further requirements could be necessary to ask a valid informed consent (e.g. trade union agreement, parents' consent, etc.) under national/sectorial legal frameworks.

2. Do you need to process personal data?

If yes, a privacy information under articles 11 ff GDPR is required.

3. Are processed data belonging to special categories under article 9 GDPR?

If yes, check if it is binding under the national/sectorial applicable legal framework to:

- Submit a protocol before the competent ethical committee.
- Undertake a data protection impact assessment under article 35 GDPR.
- Introduce specific technical and organisational measures as defined by the law.

4. Do you need to involve animals?

If yes, check:

- 3Rs requirements are fulfilled
- An ethical protocol shall be submitted under the national/sectorial legal framework.

B) Compliance by default. In order to put the technology on the market:

1. Check if any authorisation to use it is required at EU, national, local level, you will need to undertake required actions to obtain it. They may include:
 - a. To submit technical information on the developed technology.
 - b. To submit the approval from the competent ethical committee.
 - c. To pay fees.
 - d. To undertake actions within given delays.

Suggestions for the preliminary compliance activities:

- ➔ Ask for a specialist ethical-legal advice
- ➔ Allocate time, human resources, costs in the workplan

7.2. Development

This step refers to the workplan development for a technology solution. According to the risk-based approach a continuous assessment of the impact on fundamental rights shall be introduced in the life-cycle in order to be able to identify and properly implement technical and organisational safeguards to mitigate the risks identified in the preparatory activities step as well as to take actions in order to accomplish to the binding provisions stated in the applicable ethical-legal framework.

The following checklist could be followed in the development of the workplan either for the *by design* dimension or for the *by default* one.

1. Mapping the ethical legal framework applicable to the given technology. In particular, verify whether you need to comply with EU Regulations / Directives and national implementations regarding:
 - Personal data under EU Regulation 2016/679, considering the following grounds:
 - i. Purposes and means of data processing to establish how to protect the availability, confidentiality, and integrity of data.

- ii. Nature of data to combine GDPR conditions with possible national safeguards in case of “sensitive data”.
- iii. Legal basis of data also to establish the governance in case of multi-party sharing.
- iv. Conditions to process cross-border data flows.
- v. Conditions for the possible secondary use of data to check legal basis, governance, safeguards (e.g. pseudonymisation).
- vi. Contents for the privacy information to data subjects.
- Non-personal data flows under the EU Regulation 2018/1807, considering the following grounds:
 - i. Conditions to give/obtain access to data (IPRs, data ownership, etc.).
 - ii. Conditions to give/obtain access to confidential information.
 - iii. Conditions to boost open data, by developing a FAIR ecosystem where data are as open as possible (i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and as close as necessary (i.e. to protect confidentiality and privacy).
- **Sharing personal and non-personal** data flows under the Data Governance Act
 - i. **Conditions to sharing personal data**
 - ii. **Condition to sharing confidential information**
 - iii. Conditions for data altruism.
 - iv. Conditions for public services intermediaries.
- Artificial Intelligence.
 - i. If AI Act has entered into force, then meet the requirements.
 - ii. If AI Act has not entered into force yet, then undertake an assessment adopting a common tool (e.g. the ALTAI checklist, CNIL tool) to deal with the requirements of lawfulness, ethics, and robustness of the developed technology.
- Cybersecurity
 - i. **Check if you need to appoint an internal point of contact for cybersecurity issues**
 - ii. **If any national implementation of the NIS2 Directive**, or standards, or certifications have been adopted
 - **Check if you need to comply with them** to put the technology on the market.
 - iii. **In any case, check if your environment has:**
 - **Defined policies when using ICT environment, equipment and services;**
 - **Secure backups and deletion procedures;**
 - **Mobile devices are protected by passwords, antivirus, encryption, updates and patches, etc.;**
 - **Secure Networks (VPN) are used;**
 - **Software and hardware are used in upgraded versions;**
 - **Contractors are managed including a list of minimum cybersecurity requirements, monitoring activity, include NDA or confidentiality clauses;**
 - **An incident response – resilience strategy developed.**
 - i. **Warning: please justify whereas you didn't implement one or more of the previous measures.**

- ii. Check if you need to appoint an internal point of contact for cybersecurity issues
- iii. If any standards or certifications have been adopted
 - Check if you will need to formally adhere to them to put the technology on the market.
- iv. In any case, check if your environment has:
 - Defined policies when using ICT environment, equipment and services;
 - Secure backups and deletion procedures;
 - Mobile devices are protected by passwords, antivirus, encryption, updates and patches, etc.;
 - Secure Networks (VPN) are used;
 - Software and hardware are used in upgraded versions;
 - Contractors are managed including a list of minimum cybersecurity requirements, monitoring activity, include NDA or confidentiality clauses;
 - An incident response – resilience strategy developed.

Warning: justify in case you are not implementing one or more of the previous measures.

- Clinical Trials and non-clinical studies with volunteers
 - i. If a clinical study shall be developed
 - Assign time and resources to comply with the CTR and to follow local practices under the competent ethics committee.
 - Develop a protocol including the following sections:
 - Identification of roles and responsibilities between sponsor, sponsor-investigator, Principal investigator, etc.
 - Title of the study.
 - Background and rationale.
 - Objectives and Outcomes.
 - Design.
 - Population.
 - Assessments of *sub* d,e,f.
 - Safety.
 - Statistical method.
 - Data management plan (including IPRs and Data protection profiles).
 - Quality assurance and control.
 - Publication and Dissemination policy.
 - Funding and support.
 - Insurance.
 - References.
 - Annexes (informed consent templates including privacy policy, Conflict of interests declaration, agreements between organisations involved in the trial).

- ii. If a non-clinical trial shall be developed
 - Assign time and resources to follow local practices under the competent ethics committee.
 - Develop a protocol including the above-illustrated sections, namely: a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j,k,l,m,n,o,p if required by the specific study.
2. Implement the technical and organisational measures required by the applicable legal framework.
3. Establish mechanisms to monitor an effective implementation of the measures and safeguards identified under sub 2.

Suggestions for the compliance activities:

- ➔ Establish a concrete dialogue between ethical-legal experts and technical staff
- ➔ Introduce monitoring systems to verify the alignment between compliance activities and technical development of the technology

7.3. Application/Usage

During the application/usage of the developed technology sectorial legislations could require maintaining an accountable approach to monitor the ethical dimensions in order to avoid either misuse/dual use or to ensure fundamental rights protection in the concrete application usage of the developed technology. If the developer is providing services to the end user or the technology works on servers belonging to the developer, then the latter is maintaining a control on it, and in particular on data processed by the technology. Such a role shall be identified, regulated, and communicated to the end user. Therefore, compliance activities are required also at this stage. To this end, the following checklist could be useful to maintain an accountable approach also when the product is ready to be placed on the market.

1. Roles identification.
 - a. If the developer processes personal data as a data controller, then comply with the GDPR as above-described.
 - b. If the developer processes personal data as data processor/joint data controller, then enter into a data processing agreement with the data controller.
 - c. If the developer performs as a system administrator, then check if any appointments / conditions are required.
 - d. Repeat compliance activities for any secondary use of data.
2. End-users/data subjects' consent and rights.
 - a. Terms and conditions shall include a section dedicated to privacy information on personal data processing (where applicable).
 - b. Check if the consent is the legal basis of the data processing. In that case, introduce features to verify the identity in the consent collection/management procedures.
 - c. Introduce features to make data subjects able to exercise their rights.
 - d. Adapt interfaces and contents to the vulnerability of the data subject and to the possible further uses of data, in particular:

- i. if end-users are children, then check age for directly providing the service, otherwise include mechanisms to engage legal representatives.
 - ii. if end-users are patients / potential patients, then adapt information to the purposes of the technology and to the context.
 3. Monitoring and reporting mechanisms.
 - a. Introduce monitoring mechanisms to check the updates to empower technology trustworthiness.
 - b. Introduce reporting mechanisms for users.

Suggestions for the compliance activities:

- ➔ Compare Terms and Conditions with other applied for similar technologies
- ➔ Engage stakeholders / end users' representatives to evaluate the efficacy of the features introduced for consent collection and management

8. Conclusions

This document developed a protocol to address ethical legal compliance activities in Research and Innovation sectors.

In particular, it includes checklists to deal with possible ethical-legal issues emerging during a given life-cycle of the development of a not-specified technological solution in order to achieve a high level of compliance by design and by default, including cybersecurity issues.

Smart boxes suggest best practices to concretely apply the instructions.

9. Annex A – References and bibliography

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4. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
DGA	Data Governance Act
DPA	Data Protection Authority
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

Table 10 – Glossary